

**ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION:
LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF ARBITRATION IN NEPAL**

Table of Contents

PART-I.....	1
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION TO ADR.....	1
1.1 Concept of Alternative Dispute Resolution.....	1
1.2 History of Alternative Dispute Resolution.....	2
1.3 Types of Alternative Dispute Resolution.....	3
1.4 Characteristics of Alternative Dispute Resolution.....	5
1.5 Importance of Alternative Dispute Resolution.....	6
CHAPTER TWO - AN INTRODUCTION TO ARBITRATION.....	8
2.1 Concept of Arbitration.....	8
2.2 Characteristics of Arbitration.....	9
2.3 Historical Development of Arbitration.....	10
2.4 Types of Arbitration.....	12
2.5 Importance of Arbitration in Commercial Dispute Resolution.....	13
CHAPTER THREE - LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON ARBITRATION IN NEPAL.....	16
3.1 Development of Arbitration Law in Nepal.....	16
3.2 Existing Nepalese Legislation on Arbitration.....	17
3.3 Features of Existing Legislation on Arbitration.....	20
3.4 Significant Case laws related to Arbitration in Nepal.....	21
CHAPTER FOUR - ARBITRATION AND ITS PROCESS.....	26
4.1. Process and Proceedings of Arbitration.....	26
4.2 Intervention of Court during Arbitration proceedings.....	29
4.3 Stages of Arbitration.....	31
4.4 Arbitral award and its recognition as well as its enforcement in Nepal (Both Local Arbitration & Foreign Arbitral Award).....	33

PART-I

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION TO ADR

1.1 Concept of Alternative Dispute Resolution

Alternative dispute resolution (ADR) refers to a set of practices and techniques aimed at permitting the resolution of legal disputes outside the courts.¹

The term "alternative dispute resolution" or "ADR" is often used to describe a wide variety of dispute resolution mechanisms that are short of, or alternative to, full-scale court processes.² ADR programs are instruments for the application of equity, rather than the rule of law, and as such cannot be expected to establish legal precedent or implement changes in legal and social norms. However, ADR programs can complement and support judicial reforms.³ Alternative discipline as an ADR technique involves taking some type of action in lieu of traditional discipline to correct misconduct without resorting to more costly formal procedures and litigation.⁴ Alternative dispute redressal techniques can be employed in several categories of disputes, especially civil, commercial, industrial and family disputes.⁵

Aristotle rightly said in his words that Arbitration was introduced to give equity its due weight, making possible a larger assessment of fairness. Further **Cicero** said that a person going to court expects to win or lose; a person going to arbitration expects not to get everything but not lose everything either. In other words, Cicero founded win-win negotiation hundred years ago.⁶

Thus, Alternative dispute resolution refers to "a variety of approaches that allow the parties to meet face to face to reach a mutually acceptable resolution of the issues in a dispute or

¹ Robert Mnookin, *Harvard Law School John M. Olin Center for Law, Economics and Business Discussion Paper Series* (1998) https://www.researchgate.net/publication/30504345_Alternative_Dispute_Resolution.

² Scott Brown, Christine Cervenak & David Fairman, *ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION PRACTITIONERS GUIDE* https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PNACB895.pdf.

³ *Ibid.*

⁴ Michael L. Moffitt and Robert C. Bordone, eds., *Alternate Dispute Resolution Handbook*, (2005) <https://www.opm.gov/policy-data-oversight/employee-relations/employee-rights-appeals/alternative-dispute-resolution/handbook.pdf>.

⁵ Hindu Marriage Act 1955, Industrial Dispute Act, 1947, The Code of Civil Procedure, The Family Court Act, 1984.

⁶ Hümeýra Zeynep Nałçacıođlu ERDEN, *THE HISTORY OF ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTIONS IN THE UNITED STATES* <https://www.ajindex.com/dosyalar/makale/acarindex-1423908109.pdf>.

potentially controversial situation...all are voluntary processes that involve some form of consensus building, joint problem solving, or negotiation.”⁷

1.2 History of Alternative Dispute Resolution

Since the beginning of humanity, “disputes, both within groups and between them, are found everywhere in the society. Traditional societies had a kind of mediation particularly in family resolving disputes. Parties discussed their problems in front of the leadership of someone or a group who were respected elders.”⁸

Alternative Dispute Resolution, as it is known now, originated in England as early as 1066. English citizens held their own informal court to solve private disputes. Often these informal meetings were led by respected male members of the community. Sometimes, instead of trying a case in king’s court, the king would adopt the decision of the citizens. This is one of the first forms of arbitration created. In the American Colonies, mediation was more popular than traditional lawyers and courts. After the United States gained independence, arbitration was mainly used for patent claims until the 19th century when the Federal Mediation and Conciliation Service (FMCS) was created. Then, in the 1920s congress enacted the “Federal Arbitration Act”. Throughout the 20th century it grew in popularity in America and now ADR is a big part of the American Legal System.⁹

Alternative dispute resolution became popular in the middle of 1990's. At first, it was seen as a tool for the reduction of court's backlogs. With the diminishing role of national chambers of commerce-as promoters of arbitrage courts-also the arbitrage became less and less popular among small and medium size enterprises. These processes were even more radical in ex-Socialist/Communist countries with no small and medium enterprises developed. So, the new millennium with the developed IT infrastructure has brought out also new ideas about the society development.¹⁰

The first Arbitration Act was passed in the year 1698 under William III. Later, changes were made in accordance with the need.¹¹

⁷ Bingham, G., *Resolving environmental disputes: A decade of experience*. Washington, D.C: The Conservation Foundation (1986).

⁸ *Supra* note 6.

⁹ McManus, M., & Silverstein, B., *Brief History of Alternative Dispute Resolution in the USA. Cadmus: Promoting Leadership in Thought That Leads to Action*, 1(3), 100-105 (2011).

¹⁰ *Supra* note 1.

¹¹ Raghiv Naushad & Nabil Iqbal, *Tracking the History of Alternative Dispute Resolution in India* [Vol. 3 Iss 4; 235] (2020) <https://www.ijlmh.com/wp-content/uploads/Tracking-the-History-of-Alternative-Dispute-Resolution-in-India.pdf>.

History of ADR in Nepal

Nepal has a long history of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) and, as in other Asian countries, its roots stem from the practice of local communities of turning to village elders who would resolve the disputes through consultation with the conflicting parties. The practice was formalised by the Arbitration Act 1981, which was then replaced by the arbitration act 1999. Nepal has enacted and amended a number of domestic laws to promote and strengthen ADR practices in the country. These include the Contract Act 2000, the Company Act 2005. The Mediation Act 2011 and the Foreign Investment and Technology Transfer Act 1019.¹²

1.3 Types of Alternative Dispute Resolution

It is important to distinguish between binding and non-binding forms of ADR. Negotiation, mediation, and conciliation programs are non-binding, and depend on the willingness of the parties to reach a voluntary agreement. Arbitration programs may be either binding or non-binding.¹³

Therefore, the types of Alternative Dispute Resolution are described below;

a) Negotiation

Negotiation is listed first as it is an often-overlooked dispute resolution mechanism. It goes on every moment of every day across the globe in all sorts of dispute situations. It can take any number of forms, from a simple conversation to a structured negotiation forum. Negotiation is the most informal of the ADR methods and probably the most flexible as it is only limited by the framework that is enacted by the negotiators themselves. It is also the least binding as there are rarely structured or formal outcomes to everyday, low-level negotiations. In a commercial setting, many issues that may have the potential to become a dispute are resolved quickly and easily, often without the people involved being aware that they may have resolved a potential dispute in the making. The definition of negotiation can be exceedingly wide and its success is generally linked to the skill of those participating.

¹² Matrika Niraula, Mohammed Talib & Alix Povey, 'Nepal: The Rise of ADR on Paths Less Travelled ', Asian Dispute Review, Issue 1, pp. 41-46 (2022)

<https://kluwerlawonline.com/journalarticle/Asian+Dispute+Review/24.1/ADR2022007>

¹³ *Supra* note 2, p.4.

b) Arbitration

Arbitration is the most formal of the ADR methods and the process is very similar to traditional court litigation. Arbitration usually happens as a result of a clause within a contract, which will specify that in the event of a dispute the parties agree to resolve the matter through arbitration rather than litigation. This is particularly common in commercial contracts due to the fact that arbitration is a confidential process and held in private, as opposed to the public forum of a court hearing.

Arbitration is the most formal and is a well-established and utilised method. It differs from litigation in that it is the parties who select or appoint the panel and the parties who set the rules and process. Due to the formality of the arbitration process and the parallels with traditional litigation, it is predominantly undertaken by legal professionals including barristers and members of the judiciary. However, there has been an increase in professionals from non-legal backgrounds being involved in arbitrations that fall within their area of expertise or experience.

c) Mediation

Mediation is a confidential, voluntary process where disputes are resolved between the parties with the aid of a neutral-third party mediator. It is possible to have mediation clauses in contracts, although these are not as common as with arbitration. In a mediation, the parties are given the chance to reach a resolution to the dispute themselves and there is a high level of flexibility in the outcomes that can be achieved. The process is party led; the parties are integral to the resolution and are much more likely to abide by the resolution as they have created it. It is the role of the mediator to facilitate the level of communication between the parties.

Mediation is widely used for community mediation and encompasses a huge variety of disputes, including neighbour, boundary, anti-social behaviour, gang, noise, landlord and tenant, and anything that may arise in a community.

d) Conciliation¹⁴

¹⁴ Suherman, *Arbitration and Other Alternative Dispute Resolution for Commercial Dispute (Reviewed from the Strengths of ADR and Decision of Arbitration)*, Vol 6 No. 1 (2019)
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332653814_Arbitration_and_Other_Alternative_Dispute_Resolution_for_Commercial_Dispute_Reviewed_from_the_Strengths_of_ADR_and_Decision_of_Arbitration.

Conciliation is an alternative choice for parties who do not accept to submit to jurisdiction, whether it is the jurisdiction of another state or of an arbitration tribunal. It is a non-competitive method but is not a litigation. Additionally, the business relationship between the disputants is more likely to be preserved. Moreover, conciliation may even develop the relationship between the parties, "since the scope of conciliation and the ultimate agreement of the parties may go beyond the strict confines of the dispute that gave rise to conciliation.

1.4 Characteristics of Alternative Dispute Resolution

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) is a procedure providing the opportunity to settle disputes through alternative means other than those available in court room.¹⁵

The key points highlighted here can be summarised and understood as follows:

- ADR is **confidential** unless the parties agree otherwise. This means that sessions are held in private and are not reported. This can be particularly useful if a matter is sensitive, for example, for commercial reasons.
- ADR is **flexible** as it is not typically bound by the same rules in the same way that a court or tribunal would be; however, some forms of ADR, such as arbitration, are subject to rules agreed by the parties.
- ADR is usually **conducted by a subject specialist**: for example, a housing matter would be dealt with by a housing expert and a commercial matter by a commercial expert. This means that the person dealing with the case has a good understanding not only of the subject but also of the realities and practicalities of that area.
- ADR is focused on resolving the issue and how the parties can address the issue and move on, rather than what has already happened and apportioning fault or blame.
- Parties to ADR can actively participate in the process and mostly get to make the final decision, sometimes facilitated by an intermediary. In contrast, in courts or tribunals, the process is usually conducted by legal professionals on behalf of the parties and the decision is made for the parties with at times only limited involvement or understanding.

¹⁵ Louis MARTIN, *Administrative Dispute Resolution in Administrative Matters*, Istanbul Congress (2016) <https://www.aihja.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/8th-Compendium-Alternative-dispute-resolution-in-administrative-matters-EN-2016.pdf>.

1.5 Importance of Alternative Dispute Resolution

Dispute resolution procedures may be critical to economic development objectives where court delays or corruption inhibit foreign investment and economic restructuring.¹⁶

The importance of Alternative Dispute Resolution is given below;

- a) ADR supports and **complements court reform**.
- b) It gives the parties more control over the process and the results putting the **parties in control** (instead of their lawyers or the court) by giving them an opportunity to tell their side of the story and have a say in the final decision.
- c) **Increase popular satisfaction** with dispute resolution. Parties who resolve their disputes through ADR are generally more satisfied because they may directly participate in working out the terms of their settlement.
- d) It helps to **keep private disputes private** - only people who are invited can attend an ADR session, unlike court, where the proceedings are usually on the public record and others, including the media, can attend.
- e) The ADR process is **less rigid ensuring flexibility**. Unlike a trial date that can vary because of the backlog, ADR can be scheduled at any time. This not only provides greater flexibility but also helps speed up the resolution of the conflict.
- f) It creates **less friction**. Once a court verdict is delivered, it invariably leaves one side disappointed, upset, angry, and even bitter. With ADR, the process uses every opportunity to preserve the rapport between the two sides. For example, if there is a child custody case being presented, the mediator or arbitrator will not only take into account the welfare of the child, but also the relationship between the parents.
- g) ADR is usually **a lot cheaper than a trial**. Just the discovery process for going to trial can lead to an exorbitant total cost that includes court reporter fees, attorney fees, and the expenses associated with printing and mailing documents. With ADR, the process is shorter, and time is money.
- h) It ensures **faster resolution**. The court system is overloaded. It cannot hold a trial for every lawsuit that gets filed. As a result, it can take several years for a legal case to go to trial. A

¹⁶ Scott Brown, Christine Cervenak & David Fairman, *ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION PRACTITIONERS GUIDE* https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PNACB895.pdf.

settlement or arbitration award can be issued within a few weeks or months of filing a lawsuit.

Therefore, Arbitration, mediation and a variety of hybrid procedures now represent an array of other possible ways in which a third party (other than a judge) can be involved in dispute resolution.¹⁷ . In fact, ADR can help preserve a variety of relationships, including those between business partners, employees-employers, and even homeowners' association board members.

¹⁷ *Supra* note 1.

CHAPTER TWO - AN INTRODUCTION TO ARBITRATION

2.1 Concept of Arbitration

Arbitration is an alternative dispute resolution method (ADR) and is a voluntary agreement agreed to by the disputing parties and the decision also known as the arbitral award is binding upon them.¹⁸ When dispute arises during the progress of a contract it is not necessary that it should automatically go before a court of law for resolution. The parties involved may agree to submit their differences to a third party in whom they have confidence and whose decision they will accept and enforce. To resolve a dispute in this manner, without recourse to the courts, is the essence of arbitration.¹⁹

Where two or more persons agree that a dispute or potential dispute between them shall be decided in a legally binding way by one or more impartial persons in a judicial manner, that is upon evidence put before him or them, the agreement is called an arbitration agreement or a submission to arbitration.²⁰

Arbitration is a device whereby the settlement of a question, which is of interest for two or more persons, is entrusted to one or more other persons - the arbitrator or arbitrators- who derive their power from a private agreement, not from the authorities of a State, and who are to proceed and decide the case on the basis of such an agreement.²¹

By contrast, one of the biggest drawbacks of arbitration would be; unlike court judgments where parties can appeal against a decision, arbitral awards are final and binding in nature, and can be challenged only when they concern issues of procedural fairness, jurisdiction and public policy.²²

Mutual agreement between the parties and the arbitrators is at the base of every arbitration agreement. Certain duties are imposed on the arbitrators by the parties via the agreement to arbitrate, and once the arbitrators give their consent, they are bound by those duties. Sometimes,

¹⁸ Viraj Fulena & Hemant Chittoo, *International Commercial Litigation and Arbitration Research Essay*, Vol.06 (2023)https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368950537_International_Commercial_Litigation_and_Arbitration_Research_Essay.

¹⁹ Shuvan Raj Acharya, *Laws of Arbitration in Nepal*, p.182
<https://www.nepjol.info/index.php/NCCJ/article/view/20261/16649>.

²⁰ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 2(a).

²¹ David, R.: *Arbitration in International Trade*, Kluwer Law and Taxation Publishers, Deventer, p. 5 (1985)

²² Supra Note 18.

if we are in an institutional arbitration, for instance, in the International Chamber of Commerce arbitration, the ICC Rules of Arbitration will apply.²³

It differs from litigation in that it is the parties who select or appoint the panel and the parties who set the rules and process. It is particularly applicable to disputes that span international jurisdictions: awards and agreements are enforceable across different international jurisdictions through the New York Convention. The convention enables the enforcement of arbitral awards across international borders, and 160 countries are signatories.

2.2 Characteristics of Arbitration

From the foregoing definitions it may be concluded that, for a process to be recognized as arbitration, it should comprise the elements below: - Mutual consent to submit to arbitration, - Choice of arbitrators, - Due process, -A binding decision²⁴

a) Mutual Consent to submit to arbitration

Mutual consent is considered one of the fundamental principles of traditional arbitration and is crucial to the legitimisation of the arbitration process. In arbitration agreements, due consideration, valid offer and acceptance, and intention to create legal obligations should exist. It is a well-established ruling that the parties should not be forced to arbitrate unless they have freely agreed to that particular mode of dispute settlement.

b) Confidentiality:²⁵

An arbitration is heard in private. The tribunal, the parties and their representatives are the only persons allowed to participate in the proceedings unless the parties and the tribunal agree otherwise. The parties can agree that the arbitration will be confidential.

c) Choice of arbitrators

Decision makers in arbitration are usually chosen by the parties or on behalf of them. In arbitration the arbitrators chosen by, or on behalf of, the parties should be independent and impartial. The term independence is defined as “one which measures the relationship between

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Farzaneh Badiei, *Online Arbitration Definition and Its Distinctive Features* (2010) <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-684/paper8.pdf>.

²⁵ Mayer Brown International LLP, *An introduction to arbitration*, Lexisnexis(2012) https://www.mayerbrown.com/-/media/files/news/2012/12/an-introduction-to-arbitration/files/lexisnexis_2012_intro-to-arbitration/fileattachment/lexisnexis_2012_intro-to-arbitration.pdf.

the arbitrator and the parties personal, social, and financial relation. The closer the relation in any of these spheres, the less “independent” the arbitrator is from the party. The power to choose the decision maker is one of the main differences between arbitration and litigation. In litigation the judges are imposed on the parties whilst in arbitration the arbitrators are chosen by or on behalf of the parties.

d) Due process

Due process is necessarily a vital component of any arbitration definition since a procedure which lacks due process may not be recognized as arbitration. Due process in arbitration relates to the right to be heard, the right to adversary proceedings and the right to be treated equally. A limited due process is in favour of the parties in some cases, especially when more process raises costs to the point that parties who deserve to win on the merits cannot get access to adjudication and thus lose. Therefore, limited due process which may provide a full access to justice is better than a full adjudicatory process which may be a barrier for the parties to have access to justice.

e) A binding decision

By agreeing on arbitration, parties give arbitrators a judicial role to adjudicate between them and to issue an award that is as effective as a court’s decision. The binding decision distinguishes arbitration from other dispute resolution procedures, and it is the purpose of such process.

However, some legal systems explicitly allow the parties to agree that the arbitration awards have a different effect i.e. be conditionally binding.²⁶ UK arbitration law 1996 states that “unless otherwise agreed by the parties an award made by the tribunal pursuant to an arbitration agreement is final and binding both on the parties and on any person claiming through or under them.” As this is a non –mandatory provision, the parties may agree that an award should have a different effect.²⁷

2.3 Historical Development of Arbitration

Arbitration is not a recent tool designed to circumvent the drawbacks of contemporary litigation; its origins date back to primitive societies where it was favoured as a primary dispute resolution

²⁶ Harris, B., Planterose, R., Tecks, J. *The Arbitration Act 1996: A Commentary*, 3rd ed., Blackwell Publishing Oxford p.279 (2003)

²⁷ Section 58 (1) of the UK arbitration law 1996.

method.²⁸ King Solomon's famous judgment from the Old Testament stands out. Solomon proposed splitting the child in half when two mothers claimed the same child. One mother's selfless concern for the child's well-being led to the child being awarded to her, demonstrating a focus on the child's best interests.²⁹ In 1343, Magnus, King of Sweden, and Woldemarus, King of Denmark, negotiated a treaty in which they pledged themselves to arbitrate future differences of an important character.³⁰ Hugo Grotius, the "father of international law," published his greatest work, *De Jure Belli et Pacis*, in 1625. In the second and third books he wrote at some length on the history and value of international arbitration. Selecting historical instances of successful arbitration, he showed the antiquity and demonstrated the reasonableness of this method of settling disputes.³¹

The modern development of international arbitration can be traced to the Jay Treaty (1794) between Great Britain and the United States, which established three arbitral commissions to settle questions and claims arising out of the American Revolution. In the 19th century, many arbitral agreements were concluded by which ad hoc arbitration tribunals were established to deal with specific cases or to handle a great number of claims. Most significant was the Alabama claims arbitration under the Treaty of Washington (1871), by which the United States and Great Britain agreed to settle claims arising from the failure of Great Britain to maintain its neutrality during the American Civil War.³² The 20th century saw the growth of international arbitration, particularly in response to increasing global trade. Organizations like the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) and the International Court of Arbitration (ICCA) played crucial roles in developing international arbitration standards. Today, arbitration is widely used not only in international trade and investment but also in various fields such as employment, consumer disputes, and even sports. The rise of institutions like the London Court of International Arbitration (LCIA) and the Singapore International Arbitration Centre (SIAC) reflects its global reach.

History of Arbitration in Nepal

The formal legal history of arbitration law in Nepal dates back to the year 1957 AD. When the amendment made in the Act inserted a provision of arbitration in the case where the development

²⁸ Steve Lopez & J. Swarbrick *History and Evolution of Arbitration* NCR-527 Arb (2023)

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376033152_History_and_Evolution_of_Arbitration.

²⁹ Frank D. Emerson, *History of Arbitration Practice and Law*, 19 CLEV. ST. L. REV. 155, 155–56 (1970).

³⁰ Henry S. Fraser, *Sketch of the History of International Arbitration*, Vol.11 CLR pp.179-208, p.182 (1926).

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² Domke, Martin, "Arbitration", *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 19 Jul. 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/arbitration>. Accessed 19 August 2024.

board is involved with. After introducing arbitration by giving room in the Act, a trend has been established to recognize arbitration as a means of settling disputes in other Acts subsequently. Such Acts binding the system the system for settling disputes via arbitration are Nepal Airlines Act, 1962 AD, Commercial Act, 1974 AD and so on. Before promulgating the special law relating to arbitration, Nepal has been stated the scattered legal provisions in relation to the settlement of disputes through method of ADR, i.e.; arbitration and mediation in several Acts. The Nepalese Arbitration Law acquired the precise and formal recognition of lawmakers in 1981 AD through the enactment of the Arbitration Act, 1981 AD. It was the Act which was wholly concentrated with the arbitration. After being existed for approximately 18 years, now the Act has been replaced by Arbitration Act, 1999 AD., which is the prevailing law of Nepal to this effect. The Act, which has been brought in practice since 15th April 1999 AD.³³

2.4 Types of Arbitration

Arbitration comes in various forms, each tailored to different types of disputes, industries, and procedural preferences. Here are some of the main types of arbitration:

1. Commercial Arbitration

It Resolves disputes arising from commercial transactions or contracts and typically involves parties from different industries or jurisdictions. It can be domestic or international.

2. International Arbitration

It Handles disputes between parties from different countries and is often governed by international treaties and rules, such as those of the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) or the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL).

3. Ad Hoc Arbitration

It is Conducted independently by the parties involved without institutional support. The parties choose the arbitrators and set the rules. This type can be flexible but requires more effort in organizing and managing the process.

4. Institutional Arbitration

³³ Shuvan Raj Acharya, *Laws of Arbitration in Nepal*, p.182
<https://www.nepjol.info/index.php/NCCJ/article/view/20261/16649>.

It is managed by an established arbitration institution. Institutions such as the ICC, the London Court of International Arbitration (LCIA), and the Singapore International Arbitration Centre (SIAC) provide rules, administer proceedings, and often assist in appointing arbitrators. An “institutional” arbitration is an arbitration conducted under the auspices and pursuant to the rules of an established arbitral institution.³⁴

5. Fast-Track Arbitration

It is Designed for resolving disputes quickly and efficiently. It uses expedited procedures to shorten the arbitration timeline, often employed for smaller or less complex cases.

2.5 Importance of Arbitration in Commercial Dispute Resolution

Arbitration plays a crucial role in resolving commercial disputes. Here's a concise overview of its importance:

a. Flourishes trade and commercial relationship

Arbitration acts as a means of resolving differences between parties to international cross-border transactions³⁵ creating an easy way out for the traders and partners of different nations.

b. Neutrality

In international disputes, arbitration can provide a neutral forum that's not tied to either party's home country legal system or cultural norms. Proceedings can be conducted in a mutually agreed language and location ensuring no party has a linguistic advantage and not favouring either party's home territory. Neutral arbitration ensures both parties are treated equally throughout the proceedings.

c. Combination of both adversarial and inquisitorial court proceedings

This hybrid nature is particularly valuable in commercial disputes. It Allows tailoring of procedures to suit the specific dispute. Arbitrators can actively investigate (inquisitorial) and parties can present their own evidence and arguments (adversarial). Combines the strengths of both systems making it as a balanced approach.

d. Flexibility:³⁶ *Quicker Resolution, Easier to schedule*

³⁴ Miccioli, Gloria, “*International Commercial Arbitration*” American Society of International Law Journal (2008).

³⁵ Abdullah Dhaidan Alharbi, *A Critical Study to the Role of International Arbitration in the Resolution of International Business Disputes*, Vol.20, p.533 No: S12(2023).

³⁶ Suherman, *Arbitration and Other Alternative Dispute Resolution for Commercial Dispute (Reviewed from the Strengths of ADR and Decision of Arbitration)*, Vol 6 No. 1 (2019)

Flexibility is the most significant of the procedures, especially the last one. Arbitration processing has been done privately between the parties and arbitrators. The arbitrators are appointed specifically for that dispute. The parties can choose to have an arbitral process in the form of running by one organization or private procedure as ad hoc arbitration. The parties may design the processes and the power of arbitrator, as well as choosing the law which will be applied. Hence, varying of flexibility can be available more in arbitration.

e. Expertise of the arbitrator:³⁷

Another advantage of arbitration is the expertise of the arbitrator. They will be an expert on the matter, so be knowledgeable about the subject matter of your disagreement. This can be very helpful when the commercial conflict is technical.

f. Less Complicated: *Simplified rules of evidence and procedure*

Litigation inevitably leads down a long path of filing papers and motions, and attending court processes such as motion hearings. The normal rules of evidence used in court may not be strictly applied in arbitration proceedings, making it much easier to admit evidence. Discovery, the time-consuming and expensive procedure that involves taking and answering interrogatories, depositions, and requests to produce documents, maybe largely reduced in arbitration. Instead, most matters, such as who will be called as a witness and what documents must be produced, are handled with simple phone calls with the arbitrator.

g. Cost effective than Court trials:³⁸

First, Evidence in arbitration can be introduced more quickly and with less dispute. In arbitration, fewer motions are filed challenging the admissibility of evidence because court rules of evidence do not apply. judges are frequently interrupted by emergency matters that will take precedence over a trial. This problem normally has no counterpart in arbitration. Finally, in comparing bench trials to arbitration, the judge's decision may be delayed by the time it takes for the judge to be furnished with a written transcript.

h. Privacy: *Keep it out of the public eye*

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332653814_Arbitration_and_Other_Alternative_Dispute_Resolution_for_Commercial_Dispute_Reviewed_from_the_Strengths_of_ADR_and_Decision_of_Arbitration

³⁷ Clare Farmer, *Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Arbitration for a Commercial Dispute*, 23 July 2024

<https://legalvision.co.uk/disputes-litigation/advantages-disadvantages-arbitration>.

³⁸ *Supra* note 37.

Unlike a trial, arbitration leads to a private resolution, so the information brought up in the dispute and resolution can be kept confidential. This could be enticing for well-known public figures or clients in business disputes because all evidence, statements, and arguments will be completely confidential. On the other hand, in court, even if certain records will not be released, there is still a risk of some public access to potentially sensitive business information.

i. Impartiality: *Choosing the “judge”*

The parties to the dispute usually pick the arbitrator together, so the arbitrator will be someone that both sides have confidence will be impartial and unbiased.

j. Finality: *The end of the dispute*

For binding arbitration, there are limited opportunities for appeal. That gives finality to the arbitration that is not often available with a trial decision, which may be subject to appeals, new trials and further appeals.

CHAPTER THREE - LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON ARBITRATION IN NEPAL

3.1 Development of Arbitration Law in Nepal

A statute may provide that disputes of a particular class shall be determined by arbitration of a particular sort, either in every case or upon certain steps being taken by the parties. Where such a provision applies, the arbitral tribunal laid down by the statute has exclusive jurisdiction over such disputes.³⁹

Before promulgating the special law relating to arbitration, Nepal has been stated the scattered legal provisions in relation to the settlement of disputes through method of ADR, i.e.; arbitration and mediation in several Acts.⁴⁰

Some of the important special statutes providing for arbitration in Nepal's context are:

a) Development Board Act, 1957

The Development Board Act, 1956 recognized the idea of arbitration in the legal system and permitted its use in disputes involving the government and donors or construction firms.⁴¹

b) Royal Nepal Airlines Corporation Act, 1962

This Act provides that if any dispute arises regarding the contracts between the committee, managing director or any other official of the corporation and the other parties shall be decided by the arbitrator appointed by the GON. Further, it provides that arbitration shall have the right equal to a court and shall be final and binding for the party.⁴²

c) Petroleum Act, 1983

This act provides that any dispute relating to a petroleum agreement which cannot be amicably resolved shall be settled by arbitration.⁴³

³⁹ Upreti, Bed Prasad, "Evolution of Commercial Arbitration in Nepal Issues and Challenges" Nepal Judicial Academic Journal volume 2 (2002);210.

⁴⁰ *Supra* note 34, p.181.

⁴¹ Saroj Kumar Giri, *Arbitration Laws and Judicial Response to Settling the Disputes Through Arbitration in Nepal* Saroj, JOM VOL. 5 No.1 (2022).

⁴² Royal Nepal Airlines Corporation Act, 1962, Sec.23.

⁴³ Petroleum Act, 1983, Sec.20.

d) Foreign Investment and Technology Transfer Act (FITTA), 1992

This act provides that any dispute relating to foreign investment, only when there is no solution from negotiations, the rules of UNCITRAL become relevant.⁴⁴

e) Privatization Act, 1994

Section 13 of this act provides rules for the arbitration process. Parties to the arbitration agreement may be government or individuals.

f) Local Self Governance Act, 1999

According to this act, the arbitration is conducted by the local authority for the settlement of disputes relating with the allocation of resources land use, domestic violence, etc.

g) Bank and Financial Institution Act (BAFTA), 2006

This act has made the Nepal Rastra Bank as an arbitrator able to decide upon disputes arising between licensed financial institutions. Its decision is binding and final in this regard.⁴⁵

Therefore, Nepal has incorporated arbitration laws in the various act making it specific and clear.

3.2 Existing Nepalese Legislation on Arbitration

Nepalese procedure of arbitration is governed by various act and rules. Those that are described below are the major currently existing Nepalese legislation on Arbitration.

3.2.1 Constitutional Provisions

A constitution serves as a politico-legal document that embodies the supreme law of a nation. In Nepal, the Constitution of Nepal, 2072 operates as the fundamental law, rendering any laws or regulations inconsistent with it void by default. Though not explicitly highlighted, the Constitution incorporates alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms within Nepal's judicial structure through various provisions.

Article 50(k)(2) outlines policies related to justice and punishment, stating that alternative methods like reconciliation and mediation should be adopted for resolving ordinary disputes. This provision underscores the importance of ADR in Nepal's judicial system.⁴⁶ Furthermore,

⁴⁴ Foreign Investment and Technology Transfer Act, 1992, Sec.7.

⁴⁵ The Bank and Financial Institution Act, 2006, Sec.78 .

⁴⁶ Constitution of Nepal 2072(2015), Article 50(k)(2).

Article 127(2) allows for the establishment of additional institutions to facilitate ADR or adjudicate cases at the local level, as per legal requirements.⁴⁷ Schedule 8 further provides for the management of Village Assemblies, Municipal Assemblies, District Assemblies, and local courts for mediation and arbitration. These provisions collectively affirm the recognition and promotion of ADR within Nepal's constitutional framework.⁴⁸

3.2.2 Arbitration Act, 1999.

The Nepalese Arbitration Law acquired the precise and formal recognition of lawmakers in 1981 AD through the enactment of the Arbitration Act, 1981 AD. It was the Act which was wholly concentrated with the arbitration. After being existed for approximately 18 years, now the Act has been replaced by Arbitration Act, 1999 AD., which is the prevailing law of Nepal to this effect. The Act, which has been brought in practice since 15th April 1999 AD.⁴⁹

Arbitration Act, 1999 has not defined the word arbitration but it has defines 'agreement' means a written agreement reached between the concerned parties for a settlement by arbitration of any dispute relating to any specific legal issue that has arises nor may arise in the future as under a contract or not.⁵⁰ Arbitrator means an arbitrator appointed for the settlement of the dispute and the term includes a panel of arbitrators.⁵¹ The number of arbitrator should be odd and normally, 3 but 1 is also allowed where the parties determine so. In connection with the appointment of arbitrator by the parties or the court has been recognized by the Act.⁵²

An arbitrator's authority can be revoked, and his position could be made vacant. To act improperly, lacking of qualification are some grounds on which authority or arbitrator can be revoked.⁵³ The arbitrator has to take oath and has to hold essential qualification under law and agreement.⁵⁴ The qualification of law is to have contractual capacity, not to be punished under law on criminal charges, not to be insolvent, etc.⁵⁵ The Act has stated the rights and duties of arbitrator. Some of the rights are to have submission, determine the jurisdiction and procedure, to fix the venue, to seek the assistance of the court, to issue different kinds of award and the like.

⁴⁷ Constitution of Nepal 2072(2015), Article 127(2).

⁴⁸ Constitution of Nepal 2072(2015), Schedule 8.

⁴⁹ Karki, S.B., Mishra, B.P. & Parajuli, D.N. Business Law, Platinum Publication Pvt. Ltd. Kathmandu (2015).

⁵⁰ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 2(a).

⁵¹ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 2(h).

⁵² Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 5.

⁵³ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 11.

⁵⁴ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 9.

⁵⁵ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 10.

Similarly, some of the duties are to be fair, impartial, to respect the principle of natural justice, to take oath etc.⁵⁶

In case any agreement provides for the settlement of disputes through arbitration, the disputes related with that agreement or with issues coming under that agreement shall be settled through arbitration according to the procedure specified in that agreement, if any, and if not, according to the Act. In case of concerned parties to a civil case of a commercial nature which has been filed in a court and which may be settled through arbitration according to existing laws, file an application for its settlement through arbitration.⁵⁷

3.2.3 Arbitration (Court procedure) Rules, 2059

The Arbitration (Court procedure) Rules, 2059 are the rules that are drafted by the Supreme Court as a set of guidelines for courts to follow when intervening in arbitral proceedings.

The rules outline the timeline for completing various tasks and clarify the procedure that courts should follow, including the requirements that should be fulfilled in the documents⁵⁸ and also provide for the reduction of time limits in certain cases.⁵⁹

3.2.4 Arbitral Procedures Regulations of NEPCA 2072

The Arbitral Procedures Regulations of NEPCA 2072 is a legal document that are intended to supplement Arbitration Act, 2055 and sets out the procedures for the conduct of arbitration proceedings in Nepal.

An institution by the name of Nepal Council of Arbitration (NEPCA) has been established to administer arbitration and other alternative methods of dispute resolution in an expeditious and less expensive manner by arranging co-operation from the concerned sector and to do institutional development of acts and proceedings related thereto, for the settlement of national and international disputes of development, construction, industrial, trade and other nature which are to be resolved through arbitration.⁶⁰ It outlines the steps that must be followed in the arbitration process, including the initiation of arbitration⁶¹, the appointment of the arbitrator⁶²,

⁵⁶ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec.21.

⁵⁷ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 3.

⁵⁸ Arbitration (Court procedure) Rules, 2002, Rule 3.

⁵⁹ Arbitration (Court procedure) Rules, 2002, Rule 7.

⁶⁰ NEPCA Arbitration Rules, 2015, Preamble.

⁶¹ NEPCA Arbitration Rules, 2015, Rule 3.

⁶² NEPCA Arbitration Rules, 2015, Rule 15.

submission of evidence⁶³ and the conduct of the arbitration hearing⁶⁴. The rules also specify the rights and duties of the parties and the arbitrator.

Thus, Arbitration in Nepal is primarily governed by the Arbitration Act, 1999 (Act No. 4 of 1999), which provides a comprehensive legal framework for both domestic and international arbitration. The Act is influenced by global arbitration standards, particularly the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration and the New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards.

3.3 Features of Existing Legislation on Arbitration

The lacunae and the inadequacies mentioned above which were felt during the exercise of the 1981 Act for nearly 18 years led to the enactment of the Arbitration Act, 1999. This law was by and large a local adaptation of the Model UNCITRAL Law (1995).⁶⁵

The following are some of the salient features of the new Act:

- Conferment of party autonomy.
- The Act also requires the defaulting parties to pay the interest of the amount set by the Award.⁶⁶
- The provision of the Act is extensive to the devolution of rights and liabilities, even if there is death of any party, insanity, or disappearance of any party.⁶⁷
- Disqualifying persons having bad records from being an arbitrator.
- Lessening of judicial intervention in the arbitral process.
- Granting of supervisory jurisdiction to the Court of Appeal over the arbitral process.
- Fixation of time limitation for the appointment of arbitrators and submission of claim and counter claims.
- Determination of own jurisdiction by the arbitration tribunal itself; Oath taking by arbitrators.
- Emphasizing on expedient and inexpensive arbitral proceeding and

⁶³ NEPCA Arbitration Rules, 2015, Rule 26.

⁶⁴ NEPCA Arbitration Rules, 2015, Rule 42.

⁶⁵ Supra note. 42.

⁶⁶ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 57.

⁶⁷ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 38.

- Committing to adopt international trade usages and new trends in the arbitral proceeding etc.

The Act also includes mechanisms for reducing delays, the selection of qualified arbitrators, reduced court involvement, swift and minimally time-consuming procedures, mechanisms for award enforcement, and everything else that is thought to make arbitration less time-consuming than litigation.

3.4 Significant Case laws related to Arbitration in Nepal

In addition to the constitutional and statutory framework, there are case laws that have played a significant role in shaping the arbitration landscape in Nepal.

Some notable case laws related to arbitration in Nepal are:

1. Yakshyadhoj Karki v. High Court Patan and others (2076)⁶⁸

In this case, the Hon'ble Supreme Court held that:

- When an arbitration clause is included in a contract, the same is severable from the main contract and remains enforceable until disputes pertaining to the contract or performance of the contract have been resolved.
- Behaviour of one party, general communications or one-sided offer cannot be deemed to have amended the contract.
- Where the parties have not agreed to resolve disputes through arbitration, Section 3 of the Arbitration Act, 2055 in relation to resolution of disputes through arbitration would not be applicable.

2. Ramesh Bhomi v. Appellate Court, Patan⁶⁹

In this case, the Supreme Court discouraged party into its extra-ordinary writ jurisdiction, while the alternative way of seeking remedy through predefined contract is still not exhausted. This is important for the arbitration proceedings because, once the parties consent through agreement for their submission of their disputes to arbitration panel, they must follow the procedure of the arbitration in good faith.

⁶⁸ NKP 2074 D.no. 10369.

⁶⁹ NKP 2071.

3. Rajendra Man Sherchan v. Appellate Court Patan, NKP 2064:⁷⁰

The Supreme Court interpreted that under Arbitration Act 1999 the process of appointing an arbitrator must commence within three months from the date on which the dispute arose.

4. Krishi Samagri Company v. Appellate Court Patan, NKP 2064⁷¹:

The Supreme Court required the interpretation of contracts as per the agreed conditions and, in its absence, arbitrator may refer to the background of the contract, earlier correspondences, the generally accepted principles of the contract, international practices, Court precedents etc.

5. Raju K.C. on behalf of Nepal Airlines Corporation v. Appellate Court Patan, et.al. NKP 2067⁷²:

If the party has not been informed about the process of arbitration or has not been able to get the said information, he can apply to the appellate court to overturn the decision of the arbitrator as per Section 30(1) of the Act. However, in the event that there is sufficient and credible evidence that the respondent has received or such information have been ritually made available to them, he/she cannot apply for the repeal of arbitral awards in appellate courts as provided by Section 30(1) of the Act.

6. Bhanu Prasad Acharya on behalf of Nepal Government, Ministry of Finance V. Damodar Ropeways and Construction Company et al., 2067⁷³:

The Hon'ble Supreme Court, inter alia, held the following:

- Validity of an arbitral award cannot be determined in the same manner as other cases. In terms of factual interpretation, the arbitral tribunal is to be considered well informed and knowledgeable.
- The Hon'ble Supreme Court needs to conduct judicial examination of the arbitral award and decision of the Hon'ble Appellate Court to ascertain if the conditions under Section 21(2) of the Arbitration Act, 2038 have been met.
- When both parties have clearly established and agreed on certain aspects, the decision maker should not create a dispute out of such matters.

⁷⁰ NKP 2064, DN. 7823.

⁷¹ NKP 2064, DN. 7905.

⁷² NKP 2067, DN. 10586.

⁷³ NKP 2067, DN.8368

- The process of dispute resolution through arbitration is an informal and alternate process within the larger judicial process. An arbitral award must be supported by established facts, corroborating evidence and the written language of the contract. Interpretation based on prevalent laws and established principles should only be done when the contract is unclear or silent.

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7. Krishna Chandra Jha V. Dinesh Bhakta Shrestha on behalf of Sumit Prakash Asia Pvt. Ltd., 2066⁷⁴:

The Hon'ble Supreme Court held that the arbitral tribunal cannot decide on matters outside the conditions and provisions of the contract and that the tribunal does not have any discretionary powers.

8. Kantipur Publications Pvt. Ltd. v. Aastha Broadcasting Pvt. Ltd. (2013)

The Hon'ble Supreme Court in this case dealt with the enforcement of foreign arbitral awards in Nepal and emphasized that Nepal is a signatory to the New York Convention. As such, foreign awards could be enforced in Nepal subject to certain exceptions, such as if the award contravenes public policy. The case provided guidance on how the courts should approach the enforcement of international arbitration awards.

9. Nepal Rastra Bank v. Everest Bank Limited (2005)

The Hon'ble Supreme court ruled that the arbitral tribunal's jurisdiction depends on the existence of a valid agreement to arbitrate. If the agreement is found to be void or unenforceable, the arbitral award would not be enforceable. This case reinforced the requirement that an arbitration agreement must be legally valid for arbitration proceedings to be recognized and enforced in Nepal.

Cases related to non- intervention of Court in the aspect of arbitration law

In addition to the laws and legal frameworks established to promote the use of ADR, the Supreme Court of Nepal has also given several landmark Decisions concerning arbitration.

The first notable decision was *Naresh Vikram Subedi v. Chief District Officer Rolpa et.al*⁷⁵ made by the Supreme Court regarding court' non-intervention aspect of arbitration law. The case

⁷⁴ NKP 2066, DN.8128.

⁷⁵ NKP 2044, Vol.2, W.N.1568.

was based on non-intervention by the court through extraordinary jurisdiction until and unless the conditions stipulated in the concerned contract documents provided for. According to Supreme Court, the ordinary jurisdiction of a lower court was the right place to go for getting redress the grievance.

A case where the court declined to intervene in the merit of arbitral award was *Nepal Rastra Bank v. Rajendra Man Sherchan (2048)*⁷⁶ where a division bench of the Supreme Court did not intervene in the merit of the award. The court held that so long as legal questions are interpreted correctly by the tribunal, the court has no business to quash the award. The court should not go to examine the correctness of the arbitral award with regard to interpretation of fact and evaluation of evidence.

Similarly, in the case of *Umakant Jha V. Appellate Court Patan*⁷⁷, the Hon'ble Court held that the Appellate Court only has a correctional jurisdiction pursuant to Section 30 of the Arbitration Act, 2055.

Landmark Cases related on International Arbitration

a) The Rann of Kutch Case (India V. Pakistan) (1966)

The boundary dispute between India and Pakistan in the Rann of Kutch case about the Sarswati River, which flowing in the boundary of India and Pakistan via Rann of Kutch is one of the major instances of international arbitration in the post war period. The tribunal was constituted in Geneva on February 15,1966. The award by the arbitration tribunal vindicated Pakistan's position when the River Sarswati was flowing in the heart of India, adopting equity rights over the disputed the Tribunal awarded 90% of the Rain off Kutch in India and 10% to Pakistan.⁷⁸

b) Trail Smelter Case (United States v Canada)⁷⁹

In 1935 a Canadian based corporation (defendant) owned a smelter plant which emitted hazardous fumes (sulphur dioxide) that caused damage to plant life, forest trees, soil, and crop

⁷⁶ *Nepal Rastra Bank v. Rajendra Man Sherchan* Civil ad-hoc no. 37 of the year 2048 BS (SC16/3/2049 BS).

⁷⁷ NKP 2066, D.no. 8156.

⁷⁸ J. Gillis Wette, *The Rann of Kutch Arbitration*, The American Journal of International Law, jstor, Vol. 65, No. 2 (Apr., 1971), pp. 346-357.

⁷⁹Trail smelter case (United States, Canada), *Reports of International Arbitral awards*, Vol. III pp. 1905-1982, 16 April 1938 and 11 March 1941.

yields across the border in Washington State in the United States (plaintiff). The United States took Canada to court. The same year a Convention established an arbitral tribunal consisting of two national members and a neutral chairman. The Tribunal was aided by scientific experts appointed by the governments. In its first decision, 1938, the Tribunal concluded that harm had occurred between 1932 and 1937 and ordered the payment of an indemnity of \$78,000 as the 'complete and final indemnity and compensation for all damage which occurred between such dates'. The Tribunal's second decision (1941), was concerned with the final three questions presented by the 1935 Convention, namely, responsibility for, and the appropriate mitigation and indemnification of, future harm. The Tribunal concluded, with respect to future harm, that: 'no State has the right to use or permit the use of its territory in such a manner as to cause injury by fumes in or to the territory of another or the properties or persons therein, when the case is of serious consequence and the injury is established by clear and convincing evidence'.

CHAPTER FOUR - ARBITRATION AND ITS PROCESS

4.1. Process and Proceedings of Arbitration

The arbitration procedure set out in the arbitration agreement must be followed. If no procedure has been agreed, the parties must follow the procedure set out in the Arbitration Act 1999. If there are procedural aspects not defined in the agreement or the act, the parties may decide on how to proceed. If the parties are unable to agree, the arbitrators will decide on those procedural aspects.

4.1.1 Dispute settlement through arbitration⁸⁰

If the agreement comprises a detail procedure of the settlement of disputes through arbitration then the dispute should be settled pursuant to the agreement. In absence of any procedure mentioned in the agreement, the dispute should be settled as the procedure outline in the Arbitration Act. Further cases of civil suit related to commercial nature can be settled through the arbitration by mutual consent of parties.

4.1.2 Appointment of Arbitrator⁸¹

Parties to the arbitration has been given the exclusive right to choose the arbitrator(s). If the parties could not choose any, the arbitrator is appointed as per the process prescribed in the Act. Parties shall appoint one arbitrator each and the appointed arbitrators shall appoint the third arbitrator.

Appointment of Arbitrator by Court⁸²

If the parties fail to appoint an arbitrator, an application can be submitted to the High Court along with a copy of the agreement and details of minimum three persons who are to be appointed as arbitrator. The court shall appoint an arbitrator within period of 60 days after receiving the application if the parties fail to make consensus on the name of arbitrator.

The Nepal Council of Arbitration (NEPCA), a non-profit organization, is the only institution that provides institutional arbitration services. Under the NEPCA Rules, the parties must appoint their arbitrators within 30 days of the commencement of proceedings. If the parties fail to agree on an arbitrator (in the case of a sole arbitrator) or to appoint their arbitrator (in the case of

⁸⁰ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 3.

⁸¹ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 6.

⁸² Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 7.

multiple arbitrators), either party can request the NEPCA to appoint the arbitrator. However, the majority of arbitrators listed in the NEPCA have no legal background, which is an odd practice. Similarly, there are few legal professionals in Nepal qualified or experienced in arbitration, leading to insufficient candidates to meet the needs of complex arbitration.

Qualification of Arbitrator⁸³

The qualification that are required for an arbitrator are as mentioned;

- a. Have capacity to enter into a contract,
- b. Have not been punished for a crime involving moral turpitude,
- c. Are not insolvent or bankrupt,
- d. Not possessing any personal interest in the dispute and
- e. Are qualified as per the qualification specified in the agreement.

Number of Arbitrator⁸⁴

Number of arbitrators shall be as per the arbitration agreement and if the agreement is silent, three arbitrators must be appointed. Each party must appoint an arbitrator and the appointed arbitrator shall appoint a chair.

Removal of arbitrator⁸⁵

If parties intend to remove the arbitrator, then they can remove the arbitrator as per the provision mentioned in the agreement.

If the agreement is silent regarding the removable of arbitrator parties can remove the arbitrator in the following conditions:

- In case any arbitrator is clearly seen as bias or discriminated against any party instead of working in an impartial manner,
- Any arbitrator engages in improper conduct or commits fraud in the course of arbitration,
- Frequently commits mistakes or irregularities in the course of arbitration,

⁸³ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 10.

⁸⁴ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 5.

⁸⁵ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 11.

- Does not attend arbitration meetings or refuses to take part in arbitration proceedings for more than three times without furnishing satisfactory reasons with the objective of prolonging or delaying the arbitration proceedings in an improper manner,
- Takes any action which is opposed to the principles or rules of natural justice,
- The Arbitrator is found to be lacking the necessary qualifications or to have ceased to be qualified.

4.1.3 Procedure to be Adopted by Arbitrators:⁸⁶

(1) The procedure to be adopted by the arbitrator while taking a decision on a dispute shall be as mentioned in the agreement, and in case no such procedure has been mentioned in the agreement, it shall be as laid down in this Act. Provided that the procedure not laid down in the Act shall be as prescribed by the arbitrator with the consent of the parties, and in case the parties fail to reach an agreement in that connection, it shall be as prescribed by the arbitrator him/herself.

(2) The arbitrator shall start arbitration proceedings immediately after receiving all such claims, objections, counter-claims or rejoinders as need to be received by him/her.

(3) The arbitrator must inform the parties about the type of proceedings to be held, and the day and time fixed for the purpose and also keep records thereof in the concerned case file.

(4) In respect to a dispute which has been referred to three or more arbitrators, the arbitrators who are present may conduct all arbitration proceedings other than taking the final decision or issuing the final order.

(5) The arbitrator may continue arbitration proceedings and pronounce his/her decision on the basis of the available evidence even if any party does not present itself on the day and at the time of arbitration proceedings after receiving a notice pursuant to Sub-section (3).

(6) After the completion of the process of hearing, the arbitrator shall issue an order with the effect that the hearing has concluded and keep a record thereof in the case file. No evidence may be examined or the parties heard thereafter.

⁸⁶ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 17.

(7) Notwithstanding otherwise claimant in the agreement, the arbitrator must read out his/her written decision within 30 days from the date of issue of an order pursuant to Sub-section (6).

The arbitrator must hold the office immediately after his appointment or submission of dispute in case where he is named in the agreement. He needs to provide opportunity of claim, counter claim, rejoinder and hearing of the case by the lawyer; if appointed, and to the parties themselves for discussion, if the lawyer is not appointed. His award must be based on evidence. The arbitrator has to follow the law as mentioned in the agreement, if not mentioned they must follow Nepalese law as the substantive law. The arbitrator can also exercise the discretionary power, if the parties have given such power. He provides award on the basis of terms and conditions as under the contract and also considers the commercial usages related with the case and hearing should be held in cameras unless otherwise agreed.⁸⁷ Any notice to be issued in relation with arbitration, or any notice or summon to be notified in the name of any party residing within or outside the country in relation with the hearing by the arbitrator. He must deliver notice to the concerned parties by tele-fax or telegram or any other media.⁸⁸

4.2 Intervention of Court during Arbitration proceedings

The prevailing Arbitration Act, 1999 of Nepal has the following grounds for which the courts to intervene or facilitate the arbitration proceedings, including the supervisory role to be played in some of the matters. This Act had given the High Court supervisory jurisdiction over the arbitral process and the Arbitrator's appointment if required.⁸⁹

- The principle of severability is reflected in the Act.⁹⁰ The principle in Arbitration states that an arbitration clause or agreement embodied with the original contract can be separated ipso facto from the actual subject of the contract, even if an arbitrator or court invalidates the original one.
- Deposition of the case file of arbitration to the district court for the execution of the case.
- The Act gives power to the Supreme Court to make rules on arbitration.
- The review of awards by the High Court on the grounds of public policy.⁹¹

⁸⁷ Supra note 61.

⁸⁸ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 20.

⁸⁹ Anil Kumar Shrestha, *Revisiting the Core Ideas of Arbitration through Functional and Practical Measures*, Kathmandu School of Law Review (KSLR), Vol. 12, Issue 1, pp. 164-177 p.170,171 (2023).

⁹⁰ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 16.

⁹¹ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 30.

- The Act requires that the Arbitrator affix his or her signature to the oath and submit it to the High Court.⁹²
- The Act has provided the list of rights and duties of the Arbitrator. He or she must maintain the case file chronologically, which will be submitted to the district court later for record. The Act confirms the document's confidentiality and provisions that no copies of any documents may be given to anyone other than the parties without their approval.⁹³
- This act has provided power to the Court to appoint an arbitrator if the arbitration agreement has no provision regarding the appointment of if the parties to the contract are not able to appoint any arbitrator in their consensus.⁹⁴
- This act has granted power to the Appellate Court to remove an arbitrator if the parties became unable to remove the arbitrator.⁹⁵
- This act has provided the Court to take final decision regarding arbitrator's jurisdiction.⁹⁶
- This act has granted power to the court to give final decision regarding the power of the Arbitrator.⁹⁷
- If the party dissatisfied with the award is given by the arbitrator can be challenged in the High Court for invalidating it within 35 days from the date of receipt of award.⁹⁸

Therefore, here in the case of *F. Dinkar Sharma v. NEPCA Arbitration Tribunal*⁹⁹ highlighted the exceptional scenarios where a decision of an arbitral tribunal is reviewed as per Section 30 of the Arbitration Act, 2055. While there is a high degree of finality when it comes to decisions by arbitration body, the Supreme Court highlighted that the Appellate court granted jurisdiction over such cases on grounds of lack of jurisdiction to make decision, presence of an incompetent party in the agreement, formation of arbitration contrary to law, or any outcome contrary to agreement between the parties as per the Section 30(2) of the act.

Additionally, In the case of *A. Raju K.C. on behalf of Airlines Corporation v. Appellate Court Patan, et.al.*, it has been held that if the party has not been informed about the process of

⁹² Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 9.

⁹³ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 42.

⁹⁴ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 7.

⁹⁵ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 11(4).

⁹⁶ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 16.

⁹⁷ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 21(2).

⁹⁸ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 25.

⁹⁹ *F. Dinkar Sharma v. NEPCA Arbitration Tribunal*, NKP 2076, D. No. 10586.

arbitration or has not been able to get the said information, he can apply to the appellate court to overturn the decision of the arbitrator as per Section 30(1) of the Act.¹⁰⁰

4.3 Stages of Arbitration

The procedure of settlement of dispute relating to arbitration includes the following steps:

a) Submission of Claims

Plaintiff should submit their claim before the arbitrator in writing along with evidence. The Claim should be submitted within the following:

- If the time has been mentioned in the Agreement, then the Submission should be made within the time specified in the Agreement
- If the Arbitrator is appointed after disputes arises then Submission should be made within 3 Months from the date of appointment of the Arbitrator.
- In the case where any arbitrator is mentioned in the agreement then the Submission should be made within 3 Months from the date when the dispute arises and requires arbitration.

b) Counter-Claims

If time is mentioned in the agreement the opponent party should submit its objection within the timeline mentioned in the agreement. If such provision has not been incorporated then counterclaims should be made within 30 days from the date of receipt of the claim.

c) Rejoinders

The rejoinders should be submitted within 15 days from the date of submission of the counter claim. A copy of the rejoinder should also be provided to the opponent party.

d) Extension of Submission Time

In case any party fails to submit its counterclaim or rejoinder within the time limit due to circumstances beyond the control of the party, the party can submit an application to the arbitrator for an extension of the time limit within 15 days from the date of expiry of the time limit.

If the reason for the extensions seems satisfactory the arbitrator may extend the time limit as requested.

¹⁰⁰ *A. Raju K.C. on behalf of Airlines Corporation v. Appellate Court Patan, et.al*, NKP 2067.

e) Actual Proceedings

Upon receiving all claims, objections, counter-claims, or rejoinders from the concerned parties, the arbitrator initiates the arbitration proceedings. The arbitrator must inform the parties about the scheduled date and time of the arbitration, as well as the nature of the proceedings. In instances where a dispute involves three or more arbitrators, the proceedings are collectively progressed, except for the final decision-making phase. The arbitration continues the proceedings even if one of the parties is absent.

f) Hearing

After the claims and counterclaims have been heard and the actual proceedings have been finished, the arbitrator can give the final decision based on the information and available evidence. Then the arbitrator issues an order to signify the conclusion of the proceedings.

g) Written Decision

Within 30 days from the issuance of the order that provided a final decision and concluded the proceedings, the arbitrator must issue a written decision which results in the end of the issue itself.

h) Power of Arbitrator during decision making

The arbitrator can exercise following power during the decision-making process:

- To direct the concerned parties to appear before an arbitrator to submit documents, and record their statements as required,
- To record statements of the witness,
- To appoint an expert and seek their opinion or cause examination on any specific issue,
- Obtain the bank guarantee or any appropriate guarantee for foreign nationals,
- To inspect the place, object, product, structure, production process or any other related matter which are connected with the dispute,
- Sell the material or object which is likely to be destroyed or damaged after consultation with the parties,
- To exercise any specific power conferred by the parties,

- To issue preliminary orders, or interim or inter locating orders in respect to any matter connected with the dispute on the request of any party, or make a conditional decision and
- To issue a certified copy of the document.

i) The Decision of Arbitration:

Except otherwise provided in the agreement, the arbitrator should pronounce the decision within 120 days from the date of submission of claim documents. In case there are three or more arbitrators, the decision of the majority prevails.

4.4 Arbitral award and its recognition as well as its enforcement in Nepal (Both Local Arbitration & Foreign Arbitral Award)

When, after a dispute has arisen, it is put before such person or persons for decision, the procedure is called arbitration, and the decision when made is called an award.¹⁰¹

An arbitral award, irrespective of the contrary in which it was made, shall be recognized as binding and upon application writing to the competent court shall be enforced subject to the provisions of this article.¹⁰²

The award must be delivered within 120 days from the date of submission of application.¹⁰³ The award must be signed by all the arbitrators and read out as well as supplied to the parties. The dissenting opinion is also allowed. The award may include matters such as description of dispute; decision date etc.¹⁰⁴ If the party dissatisfied with the award is given by the arbitrator can be challenged in the High Court for invalidating it within 35 days from the date of receipt of award.¹⁰⁵

Execution of award

The execution must be made within 45 days from the date of issuance of award. If the award is not executed within 45 days, the concerning party may apply to the District Court within 30 days from the expiry of time limit specified.¹⁰⁶ Ordinarily, the arbitrators would make their

¹⁰¹ Bernstien, R., *Hand Book of Arbitration Practice*, Sweet & Maxwell Limited, London (1987).

¹⁰² UNCITRAL Model Law, 1985, Art. 35(1).

¹⁰³ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 24.

¹⁰⁴ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 26.

¹⁰⁵ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 25.

¹⁰⁶ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 32.

verdict within 120 days of the date of receipt of the papers. The interested parties are required to put the arbitral award into effect within 45 days of receiving a copy of the prize.

Foreign Arbitral Award

The Arbitration Act of Nepal does not define ‘foreign award’. However, it could be inferred from the language of Section 34 of the Arbitration Act that “the award taken in foreign country” is to be understood as a foreign award.¹⁰⁷

Nepal is a party to the New York Convention on Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards 1958 (New York Convention) which is an international law governing recognition and enforcement of foreign arbitral awards by the parties. Nepal became party to New York Convention on 4 March 1998 by accession.¹⁰⁸ The first legislative enactment concerning arbitration was Arbitration Act of 2038 (1981). This was repealed and replaced by the Arbitration Act of 2055 (1999) which was enacted in line with the UNCITRAL Model Rules.¹⁰⁹ Being a member of United Nations Organization, World trade Organization and other International Organizations, Nepal has approved various international standards. Nepal has accepted the UNCITRAL Model Law.

Any person willing to enforce the award made in a foreign country has to submit an application to the High Court of Nepal with original or certified copy of the arbitration award, original or certified copy of the arbitration agreement and if such agreement is in a language other than Nepali, an official translation in Nepali.¹¹⁰

The legal regime of the applicant's home country or the country where the arbitral Award is made does not preclude any arbitral Award issued in Nepal from being recognized and enforced. Similarly, if an international arbitral award is compatible with public policy, it is not upheld in Nepal, according to Section 34(4) of the Act.

¹⁰⁷ Saurav Karki, *Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards in Nepal*, vol. II, issue 1, p.58 Year 2019-20.

¹⁰⁸ *Ibid*, p.56.

¹⁰⁹ Upreti, Bed Prasad, “*Evolution of Commercial Arbitration in Nepal Issues and Challenges*” Nepal Judicial Academic Journal volume 2 (2008);205, 208.

¹¹⁰ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 34(1).

Conditions for the enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Award in Nepal

For any foreign arbitral award to be enforced in Nepal the following grounds should be satisfied:¹¹¹

1. The appointment of the arbitrator and award should have been made in accordance with the processes agreed in the agreement entered between the parties.
2. The parties to the dispute should have been duly notified as to the proceedings of the arbitration.
3. The award should be rendered only on the matter strictly entrusted to the arbitrator and in accordance with the provisions of the agreement.
4. The award should have become final and binding upon the parties as per the laws of the jurisdiction in which such award was rendered.
5. The laws of the country of the applicant or the laws of the country where such arbitration award was rendered should not prevent the recognition and enforcement of any arbitral award given in Nepal.
6. The application for the enforcement of an arbitral award should have been filed before the court of Nepal within 90 days from the date of the arbitral award.

Once the High Court is satisfied that the conditions mentioned above are fulfilled, such decision is sent to the concerned district court for enforcement.

Unenforceability of Foreign Awards

A foreign arbitral award cannot be enforced in Nepal if;¹¹²

- a. The arbitral award is in contrary to the public policy. Same has been recognized in case of Hanil Engineering & Construction Co. Ltd. (Supreme Court of Nepal Decision No.10138, 2075). It was held that the court considered arbitration award unenforceable as it was in contrary to the public policy.
- b. In case the awarded settled dispute cannot be settled through arbitration under the laws of Nepal.

¹¹¹ Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 34(2).

¹¹² Madhyasthata Ain, 2055 (Arbitration Act, 1999), Nepal, Sec. 34(4).

Landmark Case of Supreme Court of Nepal in Regard to Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Award

*Adv. Devendra Pradhan (on behalf of Hanil Engineering & Construction Co. Ltd.) v. Appellate Court, Patan, 2075*¹¹³

It was held that dispute resolution clause, such as arbitration, is considered a distinct agreement from the main contract, meaning it remains intact regardless of the status of the primary contract. Parties have the freedom to choose different laws for the substance and procedure of arbitration, even if they select a specific country's law for the contract's substance.

If a contract mandates amicable dispute resolution, parties must genuinely attempt to resolve the dispute as outlined in the contract before initiating arbitration. Ignoring this requirement contradicts the contract's intention, especially in multi-tiered dispute resolution clauses, which involve various stages of dispute resolution before arbitration. It's essential to serve separate notices for different issues as per the law's requirements, and failing to do so can render the arbitral award invalid. Additionally, ensuring both parties have a fair opportunity to be heard is crucial for upholding principles of natural justice, as an arbitral award may not be enforceable if one party's voice is not adequately heard.

A notice must be issued formally for parties to have a fair hearing. For an award to be legitimate and enforceable, a separate notification must be given at each stage of the arbitration process in compliance with the statute.

Conclusion

Arbitration in Nepal serves as a vital mechanism for resolving disputes efficiently, especially in the context of commercial and cross-border transactions. With the enactment of the Arbitration Act, 1999 (2056 B.S), Nepal has provided a legal framework that aligns with international standards, fostering trust among businesses and investors. However, challenges such as limited awareness, inconsistent enforcement of arbitral awards, and insufficient institutional infrastructure continue to hinder its full potential.

To strengthen arbitration practices, Nepal must focus on capacity building, promoting the use of arbitration through awareness campaigns, and ensuring that courts adopt a pro-arbitration approach. Establishing specialized arbitration centres and training professionals in arbitration

¹¹³ *Hanil Engineering & Construction Co. Ltd. v. Koneko Pvt. Ltd*, NKP, 2075, Falgun, dec. no. 10138, p. 2075 (2019).

and mediation can also enhance the credibility and accessibility of this alternative dispute resolution mechanism.

By addressing these challenges and fostering a supportive environment, arbitration can significantly contribute to Nepal's legal and economic development, promoting foreign investment and ensuring quicker, more cost-effective dispute resolution.

